

Role of social media in Information Dissemination among Farmers

Akshita Chadda*¹ and Deepak Chand Meena²

¹Department of Veterinary & Animal Husbandry Extension Education, College of Veterinary Sciences, Guru Angad Dev Veterinary & Animal Sciences University, Ludhiana-141004 Punjab, India

²Dairy Extension Division, ICAR- National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal- 132 001, Haryana, India

Introduction

Social media is a vital part of society in the modern era. Information and communication technology have completely changed how people think and function. The use of ICT has improved every aspect of life. ICT is incredibly powerful in emerging economies. Every day, communication is becoming more and more dynamic. There are billions of active monthly users on social media sites like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, WhatsApp etc. The use of social media is expanding rapidly in both urban and rural areas, and virtually no sector is untouched by it.

Social media are internet-based digital platforms that allow users to share and explore content. It describes the user-generated data, discussion, audio, video, and multimedia that is disseminated across digital networks

Andres and Woodard, 2013

The information demands of farmers in India are not being adequately satisfied due to the numerous difficulties faced by the sector and the shortage of personnel. There have been no major breakthroughs in raising farm production, despite extensive research in the field and the development of improved agricultural methods. Lack of knowledge about newer technologies is a significant factor among the many facts provided for low productivity. It is impossible to reach every farmer via a conventional farming dissemination method. Modern information and communication technologies (ICT) have the potential to solve the problem by providing location-specific information. Social networking is becoming more and more common in the agricultural and allied sector. Rural communities in emerging and least developed nations are also using social media more frequently. In addition to a broad range of social media tools for livestock extension and consulting services, many organizations have created apps

enabling farmers to get information on scientific livestock practices and engage clients online. The mainstream media for disseminating information to farmers include Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, blogs etc. Networks are being formed by professionals utilizing social media, and farmers are using it to communicate with clients and other farmers. All significant events in agriculture, including new developments in technology or methods, conferences, meetings, workshops, trainings, publications, and reports, usually tweeted or hash tagged on social media.

Social media and agricultural extension

Most people in the developed world use social media on a daily basis. But for many of the rural residents who have started using it, it has brought about a life-changing experience. Agricultural organizations utilize a variety of social media and find it useful for managing farms. The quickest global communication channel is social media. People in both developing and developed nations, as well as those in undeveloped nations, use social media extensively for agricultural extension. Due to infrastructure availability and economic conditions, developed and developing nations use the internet at varying rates. In order to share personal narratives or use the platforms as online news sources, farmers are becoming active on social media. YouTube is the most popular social media platform used by farmers.

Early in the morning or late at night is when you can find farmers online more frequently. Personal mobile phones, followed by personal laptops, are the most popular means of accessing social media. An average individual across the globe is said to spend 2.4 hours per day on social media. Social media may be able to give the platform for communication and engagement among stakeholder groups and institutions to promote innovation in the agricultural sector. In addition to facilitating mass-personal communication, it gives farmers a voice and a chance to interact directly with their customers, which can aid in direct marketing and greater revenues (Varner, 2012).

Present scenario of extension system

- ❖ Limited outreach: The reach of the public extension is limited in India
- ❖ Extension worker to farmer ratio in India: 1: 5000 (estimated 60 thousand extension workers) (Kumar, 2019)
- ❖ Poor infrastructure and high costs of delivering information
- ❖ On average extension services only reach 6.8% of farmers (FAO, 2012)
- ❖ Only 5.1% of the households had access to any source of information on modern technology of animal husbandry (NSSO, 2005)

Why social media

The present condition of Indian extension system necessitates the need of social media in order to build relationships between actors in Agricultural Innovation Systems (AIS), facilitate real-time client interaction, and make the promotion of extension programmes easier.

Advantages of using social media

- Simultaneously reaches large numbers of people
- Democratization of information
- Location specific, client specific and problem-oriented
- User-generated content and discussion among the community of members
- Easily accessed from mobile phones
- Brings all stakeholders onto a single platform
- Cost effective

Digital Tools in Transfer of Technology (ToT)

• Web Portals	• Mobile Telephony–SMS subscriptions	• Teleconsultation
• Smart phone based social media apps	• WhatsApp	• YouTube
• Podcasts	• Facebook	• Twitter
• Instagram	• Telegram	• MOOCs modules
• Mobile Apps of Institutes	• Village Knowledge Centers	

Limitations of social media

- Technical and educational illiteracy
- Unavailability of high-speed internet connection
- Unauthentic information
- Data charges
- Access to devices

Conclusions

ICT and social media can make significant contributions to the agriculture and allied sector's production, marketing, and long-term development. Poor and costly internet connections, as well as a lack of knowledge and experience, are obstacles to using social media. Systematic training, more affordable thin clients like smartphones, ubiquitous internet connectivity, and the availability of apps with ergonomic interfaces will improve the current status of ICT usage in general and social media usage in particular for the improvement of agriculture and allied sector leading to a better life for farmers in villages.

References

- Andres, D. and Woodard, J. (2013). Social media handbook for agricultural development practitioners. USAID and FHI 360.
- FAO Report. (2012). The state of food and agriculture. FAO, Rome.
- Kumar, R. (2019). Year-round green fodder production and conservation for sustainable dairy farming in India. In R. S. Meena (Ed), Sustainable Agriculture, Scientific Publisher. (pp. 38-54).
- NSSO (National Sample Survey Office). (2005). Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Govt. of India.
- Varner, J. (2012). Agriculture and social media. Mississippi State University Extension Service, Mississippi, USA.

